

SPE-LC-MS/MS optimisation using response surface methodology for quantification of pharmaceuticals, pesticides and organic UV filters included in water protection guidelines

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Micropollutants
Design of experiments
Solid-phase extraction
Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry
Surface water

ABSTRACT

The environmental concern about micropollutants (MPs) in aquatic environments has grown significantly in recent decades due to their widespread occurrence and potential risks to ecosystems and human health. Monitoring of MPs is crucial for understanding the status of aquatic systems, supporting risk assessments, developing elimination strategies, and informing regulatory decision-makers. However, due to the very low concentrations of MPs (usually ranging between ng L^{-1} and $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ levels), their quantification requires highly sensitive and precise analytical methods. Solid phase extraction (SPE) combined with liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) has emerged as the preferred technique for analysing MPs in water. Nonetheless, developing multi-residue analytical methods remains challenging due to the diverse nature of these compounds. Specifically, in SPE, various parameters can significantly influence the efficiency of the process and, therefore, optimisation strategies are needed to reduce time, costs and environmental impacts. This study focuses on using design of experiments (DoE) with response surface methodology (RSM) aiming to optimise, for the first time, an SPE-LC-MS/MS method for the analysis of pharmaceuticals, pesticides and organic UV filters included in the European Union (EU) water protection guidelines. The optimised SPE conditions (sample pH of 3–4, sample volume of 375 mL, and 3.5 mL of ethanol (EtOH) as the eluent) resulted in a MPs average extraction efficiency (EE) of 65 %, matrix effect (ME) of 8 %, and an absolute recovery (AR) of 73 %. Accordingly, the SPE-LC-MS/MS method was successfully validated for routinely monitoring 32 target MPs in surface water (SW) matrices.

1. Introduction

Water is vital for life and for the long-term sustainability of our planet Earth, having become a critical resource in the last decades due to factors such as population growth, socioeconomic development, and changes in consumption patterns, which have led to a considerable increase in global water consumption and contamination [1]. A significant hurdle in water pollution management is the presence of micropollutants (MPs) in aquatic environments. MPs encompass many classes of organic compounds, such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, industrial chemicals, pesticides, fire retardants, and other substances that, in general, are not effectively removed by conventional water/wastewater treatment processes despite their typically low

concentrations (typically between ng L^{-1} and $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ levels) [2,3]. As such, MPs are continuously released into receiving waterbodies [4–7], posing risks to ecosystems and human health that are susceptible to effects such as endocrine disruption, antimicrobial resistance, and chronic toxicity [8].

Given this issue, guidelines regarding MPs have been growing. Within the scope of the European Union (EU), the Water Framework Directive (WFD) [9] initiated action on this issue with Decision 2455/2001/EC [10] listing 33 MPs classified as “presenting a significant risk to or via aquatic environment”, designed as priority substances (PSs). Later, this document was updated by Directives 2008/105/EC [11] and 2013/39/EU [12], which added new substances/groups of substances and respective Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) to

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protect the environment and human health. The Directive 2013/39/EU also emphasises the importance of monitoring certain other substances for which there is no existing regulation, typically referred to as contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) [12]. The first list of CECs was established by the Decision 2015/495/EU, including 10 substances/group of substances for Union-wide monitoring of surface waters (SWs) [13]. This dynamic Watch List has been updated over the years by including substances needing more monitoring data for risk assessment, with potential risk based on predicted no-effect concentrations (PNEC), and for which at least one associated analytical method is available, as well as those recommended by stakeholders and research studies [14]. As a result, in 2018 and 2020, 2 Watch Lists were established, the second ([15]) and the third ([16]), respectively. The fourth Watch List, which was the focus of this study, was included in Decision 2022/1307/EU [17], which keeps some compounds from the previous editions due to the need for more information, while others were newly added due to their potential risk to human and ecosystem health, totalling a list of 26 CECs. Meanwhile, some CECs that were removed from the previous Watch Lists, were recently included in the 2022 proposal to revise the list of PSS in SW [18]. Additionally, a new Watch List was recently published in March 2025, also including 26 CECs, with some kept from the previous list and some new [19].

In the case of wastewater, a new EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) was recently approved by the European Commission (EC) including MPs for the first time: a total of 8 organic substances in a category 1, and 5 in a category 2 (2 being isomers) [20]. As a requirement to ensure the efficiency of quaternary treatment of urban wastewater, the percentage of removal shall be calculated for at least 6 of these substances, and the number of substances monitored from category 1 shall be twice the number of substances from category 2. The removal average percentage shall be used to assess whether a required minimum of 80 % removal has been reached [20].

Attending the evident global concern regarding MPs, developing robust analytical techniques to detect and quantify multi-residue MPs in aqueous matrices is crucial, as these methods enable to understand their occurrence, distribution, degradation and potential risks [21]. Solid-phase extraction (SPE) and liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) are the most recommended methodologies for the analysis of MPs in natural aqueous matrices [17,22]. However, analysing a broad spectrum of MPs with diverse chemical features is challenging due to the possible dissimilar recoveries and matrix effects, which rely on selecting the optimal SPE conditions, including cartridge type, volume and pH of sample, additives, and washing, elution, and reconstitution solvents. Moreover, traditional procedures for SPE optimisation are based on the conventional one-variable-at-a-time (OVAT) approach. However, this technique is time-consuming and costly, also failing to show interactions among the studied parameters [23,24]. Indeed, multivariate methods have emerged as alternatives but remain underexploited in this field [24–27]. Therefore, this study aims to apply response surface methodology (RSM) based on experimental design to optimise SPE conditions for the clean-up and preconcentration of a wide range of MPs in SW. Beyond the novelty of this approach, the list of target MPs includes relevant EU compounds, namely CECs from the fourth Watch List (Decision 2022/1307/EU) [17] and fifth Watch List (Decision 2025/439/EU), from the new UWWTD [20], as well as PSS listed in the recently launched proposal to revise the list of such substances in SW [18]. The ultimate goal is to develop and validate a SPE-LC-MS/MS analytical method to be routinely used worldwide.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and materials

A group of 39 MPs were included in this study, namely 21 pharmaceuticals and metabolites (clarithromycin, clindamycin, ofloxacin, sulfamethoxazole, trimethoprim, citalopram, venlafaxine and its

metabolite *O*-desmethylvenlafaxine, amisulpride, metformin and its metabolite guanylurea, diclofenac, carbamazepine, candesartan, irbesartan, metoprolol, hydrochlorothiazide, climbazole, clotrimazole, fluconazole, and miconazole), 12 pesticides (diflufenican, fipronil, azoxystrobin, dimoxystrobin, famoxadone, imazalil, ipconazole, metconazole, penconazole, prochloraz, tebuconazole, and tetraconazole), and 6 organic UV filters (mixture of 4-methylbenzotriazole and 6-methyl-benzotriazole, benzophenone-3, benzotriazole, butyl methoxydibenzoylmethane (BMDBM, also known as avobenzene), and octocrylene). **Table S1** (Supplementary Material) shows the class, subclass, molecular structure, molecular weight, (Mw) and pKa of all these analytes. All reference standards (> 98 % purity) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany), Honeywell, Riedel-de Haën™ (England), and TCI Europe N.V. (Switzerland), while internal standards (carbamazepine-*d*10, ciprofloxacin-*d*8, citalopram-*d*6, ofloxacin-*d*3, prochloraz-*d*7, and venlafaxine-*d*6) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany) and LGC Standard (England).

Individual stock solutions of each reference or internal standard were prepared by dissolving known quantities of each standard in acetonitrile (ACN) at a concentration ranging from 500 to 1200 mg l⁻¹. Each of these solutions was then diluted to 10 mg l⁻¹ and 1 mg l⁻¹ to be used in the optimisation of mass spectrometry parameters. Two working solutions containing all the reference or the internal standards at concentrations of 2.5 mg l⁻¹ and 5 mg l⁻¹, respectively, were prepared by dilution in ACN. These solutions were diluted and used to optimise and validate the SPE-LC-MS/MS method.

Ethanol (EtOH) was obtained from Fisher Scientific (Leicestershire, UK), while methanol (MeOH) and ACN were acquired from VWR International (Fontenay-sous-Bois, France). Sodium hydroxide, sulfuric acid, and formic acid were supplied by Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Oasis® Hydrophilic-Lipophilic-Balanced (HLB) cartridges (150 mg, 6 mL) were acquired from Waters (Milford, Massachusetts, USA). Glass-fibre filters (1.2 µm, 47 mm GF/C) used to filter SW samples before SPE extraction were supplied by Whatman™ (UK).

2.2. Apparatus

The target MPs were determined using an integrated apparatus from Shimadzu Corporation (Tokyo, Japan), which combines LC and tandem MS detection. The LC system comprises a Nexera ultra-high performance analytical chromatography (UHPLC) module equipped with 2 LC-30AD pumps, a SIL-30AC autosampler, a CTO-20AC oven, a DGU-20A 5R degasser, and a CBM-20A system controller equipped with LC Solution Version 5.41SP1 *Software*. The MS detector includes a triple quadrupole (QqQ) mass spectrometer detector LCMS-8040 Ultra-Fast Mass Spectrometry, with electrospray ionisation under both positive and negative ionisation modes. Argon gas was set as the collision-induced dissociation gas at 230 kPa. In addition, the SPE procedure was always carried out using a 20-position extraction manifold supplied by Waters (Milford, MA, USA), the extracts being evaporated in a CentriVap® Concentrator from LABCONCO (Kansas City, USA).

A Milli-Q water system (resistivity > 18.2 MΩ cm at 25 °C) from Millipore (Massachusetts, USA) was used to provide ultrapure water (UPW) and a multiparameter C6010 probe from Consort bvba (Belgium) was used for pH adjustments. The vacuum pump used during the SPE procedure was obtained from ILMVAC GmbH (Ilmenau, Germany).

2.3. Analysis of target MPs

2.3.1. Optimisation of LC-MS/MS conditions

A LC-MS/MS analytical method was developed and optimised aiming to include the 39 target MPs for posterior monitoring in aqueous matrices. Firstly, 1 µL of the individually prepared standard stock solutions (with concentrations of 1 or 10 mg l⁻¹) was directly injected into the mass spectrometer to select the precursor ion through full scan mode, to choose the most abundant fragments and to optimise the mass

spectrometer parameters for each substance, namely the declustering potential, collision energy, and collision cell exit potential (Table S2, Supplementary Material). The most abundant fragment (multiple reaction monitoring, MRM1) was used for quantification, whereas the second most abundant fragment (MRM2) was used to confirm the identity of each analyte. The nebulising gas flow and drying gas flow were set at $2.8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $14 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively, whereas heat block and desolvation line temperatures were respectively set at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. After selecting the MS parameters, the mobile phase was optimised to obtain the best separation and resolution for MPs under analysis. Different gradients of mobile phase were tested, by using different proportions of UPW and MeOH, both acidified with 0.1 % formic acid.

2.3.2. Optimisation of SPE protocol

The SPE was performed with Oasis® HLB cartridges (150 mg, 6 mL) due to their versatility and suitability for extracting organic compounds with a wide range of physicochemical characteristics, as those included in this study (Table S1, Supplementary Material). The cartridges were not conditioned, as this step is not required to activate this specific sorbent, according to the supplier and confirmed by laboratory tests of our research team (data not shown).

To maximise SPE efficiency and achieve the highest recovery percentage for the group of target MPs, 4 variables were considered for optimisation, namely: (A) elution solvent, (B) sample volume, (C) pH, and (D) volume of elution solvent. The best conditions for these parameters were selected based on the evaluation of absolute recoveries (ARs), extraction efficiencies (EEs), and matrix effects (MEs) of each target analyte under different tested conditions. ARs, EEs and MEs were determined by Eqs. (1)-(3), respectively (Fig. 1), through the results from combined SPE-LC-MS/MS analysis. Specifically, the ARs of MPs in the entire analytical process were assessed by comparing the peak areas of the analytes in the reconstituted SPE extracts of pre-spiked water matrix to which the peak areas obtained in the blanks of the same aqueous matrix samples were subtracted, with the peak areas of the analytes in MeOH/UPW (80:20, v/v) solutions containing the target analytes at a concentration equivalent to the theoretical of the reconstituted extracts (Eq. (1); Fig. 1). The EE of MPs during SPE process was determined by comparing the peak areas of the analytes in the reconstituted SPE extracts of spiked UPW samples, with the peak areas of the

analytes in MeOH/UPW (80:20, v/v) solutions containing the target analytes at a concentration equivalent to the theoretical of the reconstituted extracts (Eq. (2); Fig. 1). MEs were determined by subtracting the EE from the AR (Eq. (3); Fig. 1), allowing us to understand the influence of the inherent components that are naturally present in the environmental matrix on the ionisation source. Negative values of ME indicate that the matrix causes ion suppression and a loss of analyte signal, whereas positive values of ME indicate ion enhancement signal.

Firstly, the only categorical/non-numerical variable, *i.e.*, the elution solvent (A) – EtOH, ACN, or MeOH – was selected using the same procedure described elsewhere [28]. For this initial set of SPE experiments, which aims to test 3 types of elution solvents (duplicates, $n = 18$), 250 mL aliquots of both pre-filtered SW (collected from a river in Northern Portugal) and UPW (adjusted to pH 3) were spiked with 250 μL of a solution containing all analytes at a concentration of $50 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ ($n = 12$; except blank SW samples ($n = 6$)). Following sample passage, washing (4 mL UPW), and drying using a vacuum pump, the cartridges were eluted with 4 mL of each tested elution solvent. After elution, the extracts were dried using the CentriVap® Concentrator, and reconstituted in a mixture of 250 μL MeOH/UPW (80:20, v/v), which was filtered through $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) hydrophobic syringe filters (Membrane Solutions, Texas, USA). Other type of filters (polyvinylidene difluoride, PVDF, $0.22 \mu\text{m}$, Membrane Solutions, Texas, USA) were previously tested in preliminary experiments to assess possible analytes loss (data not shown); however, PTFE hydrophobic performed better.

In a subsequent stage, the *Minitab 19 software* (Minitab Statistical Software, Pennsylvania, USA) was applied, using design of experiments (DoE), process of responses and evaluation of statistical significance to define the optimal conditions for the other 3 variables, namely sample volume (B), sample pH (C), and elution solvent volume (D). RSM based on Central Composite Design (CCD; *Face centred; 2-block; 3 variables; Duplicates; Randomization*), which is commonly employed as the preferred method for response surface DoE [24,25,29], was applied. A design of 3 factors at 3 levels ($-1, 0$ and 1) was conducted, with specific details provided in Table 1. The results can relate the EE with the variables under study through a polynomial model, with only those demonstrating statistically significant (*i.e.*, $p < 0.05$) being considered. This second set of SPE experiments ($n = 32$; Table 1) was performed by

Fig. 1. Illustrative scheme describing the determination of absolute recovery (AR), extraction efficiency (EE), and matrix effect (ME) percentages, along with their respective equations (Eq. (1)-(3)). Circles correspond to analytes of interest and stars represent matrix interferents.

Table 1

DoE showing the conditions tested for SPE optimisation obtained by RSM, including (B) sample volume (mL), (C) pH, and (D) volume of elution solvent (mL). The code values are given in parentheses, and the centre points of the CCD plan are marked in bold.

n	B: Sample volume (mL)		C: pH		D: Elution solvent volume (mL)		n	B: Sample volume (mL)		C:pH	D:Elution solvent volume (mL)		
1	250	(-1)	3	(-1)	2	(-1)	17	625	(0)	6	(0)	3	(0)
2	250	(-1)	3	(-1)	4	(+1)	18	625	(0)	6	(0)	3	(0)
3	250	(-1)	3	(-1)	2	(-1)	19	625	(0)	6	(0)	4	(+1)
4	250	(-1)	3	(-1)	4	(+1)	20	625	(0)	6	(0)	2	(-1)
5	250	(-1)	6	(0)	3	(0)	21	625	(0)	9	(+1)	3	(0)
6	250	(-1)	6	(0)	3	(0)	22	625	(0)	9	(+1)	3	(0)
7	250	(-1)	9	(+1)	4	(+1)	23	1000	(+1)	3	(-1)	2	(-1)
8	250	(-1)	9	(+1)	2	(-1)	24	1000	(+1)	3	(-1)	4	(+1)
9	250	(-1)	9	(+1)	2	(-1)	25	1000	(+1)	3	(-1)	2	(-1)
10	250	(-1)	9	(+1)	4	(+1)	26	1000	(+1)	3	(-1)	4	(+1)
11	625	(0)	3	(-1)	3	(0)	27	1000	(+1)	6	(0)	3	(0)
12	625	(0)	3	(-1)	3	(0)	28	1000	(+1)	6	(0)	3	(0)
13	625	(0)	6	(0)	3	(0)	29	1000	(+1)	9	(+1)	4	(+1)
14	625	(0)	6	(0)	4	(+1)	30	1000	(+1)	9	(+1)	4	(+1)
15	625	(0)	6	(0)	2	(-1)	31	1000	(+1)	9	(+1)	2	(-1)
16	625	(0)	6	(0)	3	(0)	32	1000	(+1)	9	(+1)	2	(-1)

spiking UPW with 250 μL of a solution containing all analytes at 50 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$. The sample pH was adjusted using either sulfuric acid (95 %) or 0.02 M and 0.25 M of sodium hydroxide solutions, depending on the pH tested (variable C: 3, 6, or 9, respectively). After loading a given volume (variable B: 250, 625, or 1000 mL) of spiked UPW samples (except blanks), the sorbent was washed with 4 mL of UPW, and then dried during 45 min under vacuum. Similarly to the protocol described above, after elution with a given volume of the pre-selected solvent (variable D: 2, 3, or 4 mL), samples were evaporated in the CentriVap® Concentrator and the dried extracts were reconstituted in 250 μL of MeOH/UPW (80:20, v/v) and filtered by 0.22 μm PTFE hydrophobic syringe filters. The optimal conditions determined with UPW samples were then confirmed by triplicate assays with this matrix. In addition, these conditions were tested in 3 independent replicates of SW (the same matrix used in the selection of the most suitable solvent).

2.3.3. Validation of SPE-LC-MS/MS analytical method

In order to validate the SPE-LC-MS/MS analytical method, the following parameters were validated in accordance with international guidelines [30] and other relevant published literature on the topic [31, 32]: selectivity, linearity, range, detection and quantification limits, accuracy, and precision. Moreover, the AR (Eq. (1)), the EE (Eq. (2)), and the ME (Eq. (3)) for each analyte were assessed using the optimised SPE-LC-MS/MS methodology.

Selectivity was evaluated by comparing the chromatograms of the target analytes in a MeOH/UPW solution (80:20, v/v) with those of the same compounds in the extracts of spiked SW samples. Linearity was determined within a range of concentrations of analytes (0.2 to 333 ng l^{-1}) using triplicate matrix-matched calibration curves. For that, different volumes of the working standard solution containing all target MPs (2.5 mg l^{-1}) and a constant volume (20 μL) of the internal standard stock solution containing all the surrogate standards (5 mg l^{-1}) were spiked into SW samples. Afterwards, the extraction was carried out according to the pre-optimised SPE conditions. Accuracy and intra- and inter-batch precision were determined by injecting the triplicates of quality controls (QCs) that consisted in the reconstituted SPE extracts of spiked SW samples containing all MPs at 3 different concentrations: 13, 67, and 267 ng l^{-1} . For accuracy, the percentage of agreement between the concentrations of standards analysed in the SPE extracts and their nominal concentrations was assessed. Intra-day and inter-day precision were determined by calculating the relative standard deviation (RSD) derived from the triplicate measurements of QCs, within the same day or between three different days, respectively. Method detection and quantification limits (MDL and MQL) were directly obtained through the LabSolutions™ LCMS Software, using the S/N ratio of the lowest points of the matrix-matched calibration curves, while instrumental detection

and quantification limits (IDL and IQL) were determined as follows:

$$IDL = \frac{MDL \times f}{\frac{AR (\%)}{100}} \quad (4)$$

$$IQL = \frac{MDL \times f}{\frac{AR (\%)}{100}} \quad (5)$$

where f corresponds to the concentration factor (1500) and AR (%) is determined according to Eq. (1) (section 2.2.2).

After validation, the SPE-LC-MS/MS analytical method was applied to analyse MPs in SW samples collected from the Leça River (Matosinhos) in August 2023. Upon collection, the samples were stored in decontaminated and pre-rinsed amber glass bottles, transported at 4 °C to the laboratory, and refrigerated until being processed for MPs analysis in <48 h.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. LC-MS/MS conditions

The mass spectrometer parameters were optimised for 36 out of the 39 MPs under study, since guanlyurea, famoxadone, and benzophenone-3 were not effectively fragmented in the MS. Indeed, famoxadone and benzophenone-3 can be more easily analysed by GC due to their physicochemical characteristics, as described in other published works [33, 34]. Regarding the precursor ion selection by full scan mode, 7 target compounds were ionised under negative ionisation mode (molecular ion [M-H]⁻), while the other compounds were ionised under positive ionisation mode, with the molecular ion being [M+H]⁺ or [M+Na]⁺ (Table S2, Supplementary Material). During the optimisation of fragmentation, the parameters declustering potential, collision energy, and collision cell exit potential were selected. Two or more fragments of the precursor ion were detected for all the compounds, with the most intense transition (MRM1) being selected for quantification purposes. The retention time and the ion ratio between MRM1 and the second most intense transition MRM2 (MRM1/MRM2) were used to confirm the identity of these compounds in accordance with European regulations [30]. A summary of all these results can be found in Table S2 (Supplementary Material).

Following the determination of MS conditions, a method using a Kinetex™ 1.7 μm F5 (pentafluorophenyl) 100 Å (100 \times 2.1 mm, i.d.) chromatographic column provided by Phenomenex, Inc. (California, USA), previously developed in our laboratory to analyse fungicides, was tested for the chromatographic separation of the target MPs. The Kinetex™ F5 column was selected due to its hybrid silica-based stationary phase with phenyl groups, providing high versatility in a wide

pH range (1.5 – 8.5), which makes it suitable for separating polar, acidic, and basic compounds [35]. The pre-developed method involved a mobile phase composed by a gradient of UPW and MeOH, both acidified with 0.1 % of formic acid (Fig. 2a, Gradient 1). The flow rate was set at 0.2 mL min⁻¹, the column oven temperature was kept at 30 °C, and the autosampler at 15 °C. As expected, the chromatographic resolution could be improved after a first screening (Fig. 2a₁), and thus, the method was further optimised for this purpose. Accordingly, the gradient of the mobile phase was modified (Fig. 2a₂ and 2a₃), aiming to ensure a better chromatographic separation and, consequently, the detection sensitivity. In the first attempt to modify the gradient (i.e., Fig. 2a₂, Gradient 2), the number of gradient steps was reduced, and the analysis time was increased from 30 to 60 min, leading to a smoother gradient. Nevertheless, a peak fronting was observed for trimethoprim (Fig. 2a₂). Finally, considering that all compounds were detected within the first 27.5 min, the gradient of UPW/MeOH was adjusted and the analysis time was reduced from 60 to 36 min (Fig. 2a, Gradient 3). All the target analytes were tested (Fig. 2a₃), the compounds were properly separated with sufficient resolution of the peaks dispersed along the run time. Thus, the optimal chromatographic conditions were established by applying UPW and MeOH, both acidified with 0.1 % of formic acid, at a flow rate of 0.20 mL min⁻¹ using 10 µL as injection volume. In addition, the solvent profile over time consisted of 5 % MeOH for 0.20 min, followed by a linear increase from 5 % to 98 % MeOH over 29.8 min, maintained for 2 min. Posteriorly, there was a rapid decrease from 98 % MeOH to 5 % in 0.1 min, followed by another equilibration period of 5 min, resulting in a total run of 36 min (Fig. 2a, Gradient 3).

3.2. SPE protocol

The loading, washing, and elution steps of SPE have a strong impact on the MPs analysis either due to the influence on the AR or ME of each analyte. In this sense, making proper qualitative and quantitative

choices are of utmost importance, mainly when a wide range of analytes are targeted. However, optimising SPE for multi-residue analysis is challenging due to the numerous variables involved and their mutual dependence. To optimise the process, the single non-numerical variable, i.e., the elution solvent (A), was first studied. Subsequently, using the DoE, the remaining variables (i.e., sample volume (B), sample pH (C), and elution solvent volume (D)) were defined, by relying on RSM to maximise AR and reduce ME for the group of 36 studied compounds. EtOH, ACN, and MeOH were tested and compared as eluting solvents by analysing their respective ARs and MEs for each compound (Fig. 3).

It is important to note that out of the initial 36 target analytes, 4 of them (metoprolol, metformin, sulfamethoxazole, and diflufenican) showed non-reproducible values of AR (data not shown) and were consequently not included in the final list of target compounds. Among the remaining 32 MPs, within the group of UV filters, 4-methylbenzotriazole, 6-methyl-benzotriazole, and benzotriazole were those giving better ARs, which were higher when EtOH (76 – 80 %) or MeOH (65 – 73 %) were used instead of ACN (37–51 %) (Fig. 3a). Other works have also reported high recoveries of benzotriazoles in river water [36] and wastewater [37], albeit under different conditions such as using MAX cartridges eluted with MeOH/acetone (7:3, v/v) [36], or graphene sponge (GS)-based cartridges eluted with acetone [37]. Indeed, several studies have focused on the development of analytical methods for the determination of benzotriazoles in environmental samples, namely SPE-LC-MS/MS, as demonstrated in 2 review articles [38,39]. Nevertheless, information on SPE-LC-MS/MS methods that include benzotriazoles simultaneously with other classes of compounds is still scarce, highlighting the relevance of the results obtained in this work. On the contrary, the ARs of 2 other compounds belonging to the same class, BMDMB and octocrylene, were very low (6 – 10 % and 4 – 12 %, respectively), but reproducible regardless of the solvent.

These values are much lower than those reported in a study on SPE-LC-MS/MS optimisation for UV filters in an urban lake water, where

Fig. 2. (a) Tested gradients of UPW/MeOH, both acidified with 0.1 % of formic acid (Gradient 1 (pink), Gradient 2 (blue), and Gradient 3 (black)), and resulting chromatograms of the target compounds (a₁) Gradient 1; (a₂) Gradient 2; and (a₃) Gradient 3. Conditions: Kinetex™ 1.7 µm F5 (pentafluorophenyl) 100 Å; flow rate of 0.2 mL min⁻¹; 10 µL of injection of standards diluted in MeOH/UPW (80/20, v/v).

Fig. 3. Absolute recovery (AR) and matrix effect (ME) (a and b, respectively) obtained for 32 MPs in the SPE-UHPLC-MS/MS method, when using different SPE eluents: EtOH (blue), ACN (black), and MeOH (grey). SPE conditions: OASIS® HLB (150 mg, 6 mL) cartridges; 250 mL of SW adjusted to pH 3; 4 mL of UPW as washing solvent (# Compounds included in the Watch List 2022, ## Compounds included in the Watch List 2025, * compounds included in the new EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), + compounds included in the proposal for a new list of PSs in Water Framework Directive).

recoveries of 99 % for BMDBM and 96 % for octocrylene were achieved with ethyl acetate as eluting solvent [40]. Since this work intends to include a wide range of multi-class MPs, the comparison of the present recoveries with those of studies focused only on UV filters is difficult, as in those cases the physicochemical properties of the compounds are similar, facilitating the adjustment of conditions to achieve overall better recoveries. In this sense, the selection of the elution solvent, when considering the 5 studied UV filters, was governed by the differences found for benzotriazoles for which both EtOH and MeOH could be selected due to their similar AR values. From the analytes belonging to the pesticides class, fipronil and prochloraz stand out for their quite high recoveries when using ACN, which also performed better to recover ipconazole, metconazole, penconazole, and tetraconazole. Conversely, tebuconazole had a higher AR when eluted by EtOH, while azoxystrobin, dimoxystrobin, and imazalil had very similar recoveries for the 3 elution solvents, although MeOH performed slightly better. Indeed, high recoveries (> 78 %) of these pesticides (except dimoxystrobin) have been reported in SWs, mainly using MeOH as elution solvent [41–43]. These studies used Oasis HLB and Strata X cartridges, both of which showed good recoveries for the target compounds. Nonetheless, according to Nakhjavan, Bland [42], Oasis HLB were preferred over Strata X due to their higher retention of the target compounds. Regarding the group of pharmaceuticals, high ARs with EtOH, MeOH and ACN were achieved in general. However, some exceptions were verified; for instance, clarithromycin, ofloxacin, diclofenac, candesartan, and irbesartan gave very low recoveries in ACN and these compounds were extracted with higher efficiency with MeOH, except irbesartan for which EtOH performed better. Hydrochlorothiazide, in turn, stands out for its high AR when

using either ACN or EtOH. For most target pharmaceuticals, the effect of the strength of the applied elution solvents led to quite similar ARs; however, for most of the above-mentioned exceptions, the more polar solvents (*i.e.*, MeOH and EtOH) performed better than ACN.

Although the importance of the sample preparation in minimising or eliminating the co-extraction of matrix interferences and optimising instrumental signal [44], Fig. 3b revealed MEs ranging from approximately -70 % to +30 %, indicating either enhancement or suppression of the analyte signals. In most cases, the matrix suppressed the signal, but generally at very low levels [45]. Within the exceptions, the analytes that were most affected by matrix interferences were dimoxystrobin when eluted by MeOH (-72 %), imazalil when eluted by ACN (-51 %), and penconazole when eluted by EtOH (-70 %). Considering the quite high suppression verified for these compounds, it can be suggested that the loss in the AR is due to the ME rather than the EE of the procedure itself. As commented in a review article by Panuwet, Hunter [46], SPE can particularly contribute to ion suppression in electrospray ionisation LC-MS/MS, which is in agreement with the obtained results. Despite the intensive matrix clean-up by SPE, some interfering compounds with similar functional groups to those of the target analytes may be retained and concentrated, thus affecting the ionisation of the target analytes [45]. EE is highly dependent on the specific analyte. In particular, the elution solvent should be strong enough to disrupt the interaction between each target substance and the solid phase, whether polar or non-polar, depending on whether SPE is performed in normal phase (NP-SPE) or reversed phase (RP-SPE) [23,47]. Therefore, its selection should be tailored to each compound, primarily based on its polarity [47,48]. A solvent with polarity similar to that of the analytes ensures

efficient elution, meaning that polar compounds elute better with polar solvents in NP-SPE, while nonpolar compounds elute better with nonpolar solvents in RP-SPE [49,50]. However, when developing a multi-residue analytical method, the selection of solvent will depend on those that result in better efficiencies for the entire group of compounds. In this sense, since no solvent stands out with both substantially higher recovery and low ME, and considering that EtOH is a more environmentally friendly solvent with lower toxicity [51,52] compared to ACN and MeOH, EtOH was selected for the next experiments.

After the selection of EtOH as the eluting solvent, the numerical variables of sample volume (B: 250, 625, or 1000 mL), sample pH (C: 3, 6, 9), and elution solvent volume (D: 2, 3, or 4 mL) were defined following the DoE (Table 1; Table S3). Fitting a model using the RSM to maximise the average EE of all target MPs was not possible, since the analysis of variance showed only 1 significant variable ($p < 0.05$), making it impossible to calculate the maximum function value. Specifically, the p -values were 0.001 for the sample pH (i.e., the significant variable), and 0.437 and 0.454 for sample and elution solvent volumes, respectively. Despite the attempts to cluster the compounds by classes (pharmaceuticals, pesticides, and UV filters), the fitting model for each class also showed pH as the only statistically significant variable (data not shown). Interestingly, another study on SPE-LC-MS/MS optimisation using RSM to determine neonicotinoids in SW has also identified sample pH as the only significant variable for the compounds under study [29]. Since no model could be obtained, a parametric study was conducted involving the combination of the variables under study (Fig. 4). Analysis of contour graphics and data cross-referencing (Figure 4; Table S3) revealed that the interaction of non-significant variables B and D (i.e., sample and elution solvent volumes) had no impact on the EE of MPs (Fig. 4a). On the contrary, interactions involving pH codes between $ca.$ -1 and -0.1 (corresponding to pH values from 3 to 6) demonstrated significantly improved EEs ranging from 60 % to 65 % (Figs. 4b and 4c). Furthermore, considering that the next-level curve (> 65 %) would intercept the left lower and upper regions of the graphs, respectively in Figs. 4b and 4c, optimal EEs were predicted for sample volume codes between -1 and -0.5 (corresponding to sample volume values between 250 and 438 mL), elution solvent volume codes between 0.5 and 1 (corresponding to elution solvent volume values between 3.5 and 4 mL), and pH codes between -1 and -0.75 (corresponding to pH values between 3 and 4). To decide on the best pH for acidification pH 3 and 4 was compared; however, EEs were similar. Therefore, this range was defined for the acidification step in sample preparation.

A sample volume of 375 mL, from the optimised range of 250–438 mL, was selected as it is adequate to achieve a high concentration factor for the samples while avoiding excessive sample loading volume and time. Considering that the SPE sorbent has a maximum capacity to retain the analytes, the breakthrough volume (V_B), which refers to the sample volume that can be loaded on the sorbent bed without losing them,

should not be surpassed [53]. Therefore, a volume lower than the maximum optimised was selected taking into account the possible partial breakthrough volume at several binding sites, the high loading time [49], and the potential MEs due to the higher pre-concentration of the matrix components [44].

Within the range of 3.5–4 mL, the volume of elution solvent was set at 3.5 mL to minimise EtOH consumption, while ensuring effective desorption of MPs from the cartridge sorbent. It is important to mention that in cases where a large volume of eluent is used, the excess solvent does not affect the outcome, as the analyte has already eluted with a certain amount of solvent [49].

Finally, the pH of the samples was defined to be in the range of 3–4. In fact, pH can be one of the most critical factors controlling the retention and elution of the analyte. Generally, in RP-SPE, the pH of charged ionisable compounds should be adjusted to 2 units above or below their pK_a , depending on the charged group, i.e., basic or acid compounds, aiming to neutralise them and favour the interaction with the sorbent material [54]. As expected, the multi-class group of 32 target MPs showed a wide range of pK_a values (0.63–15.96; Table S1, Supplementary Material), with the DoE revealing that an acidic pH (3–4) generally results in better recoveries of the target MPs. Applying RSM for SPE optimisation of a wide range of MPs is still a poorly explored topic. Thus, contrary to expectations, no correlation was found between the variables, and it was not possible to establish a fitting model to determine the maximum EE, possibly due to differences between multi-class compounds. Nonetheless, DoE was useful to identify the most suitable conditions of the studied parameters through qualitative analysis, which should be taken into account in future works when model fitting is negligible.

3.3. SPE-LC-MS/MS method validation

The internal calibration method was chosen, and the samples were spiked with isotopically labelled internal standards before extraction. Although ideally each compound would have its respective internal standard, this approach can be very expensive for routine environmental monitoring. In addition, it can be challenging to find suitable internal standards for each compound in multi-residue methods, specifically when dealing with several compounds with distinct properties. Therefore, target MPs were clustered, and specific internal standards were used based on their physicochemical characteristics (Table S2, Supplementary Material), as already published in other works including multi-class MPs [28,55–57]. For the method validation, 9 calibration points were performed in triplicate ($n = 27$) using spiked SW at $ng\ L^{-1}$ levels (0.2, 0.7, 3, 13, 33, 50, 67, 100, 167, 217, 267, and 333 $ng\ L^{-1}$). Triplicate blanks were also considered. Additionally, triplicate QCs at 3 different concentrations (13, 67, and 267 $ng\ L^{-1}$) were analysed in 3 distinct days.

Fig. 4. Results of the parametric study combining the variables under analysis for SPE optimisation, demonstrated by extraction efficiency (EE) contour graphics: (a) Elution solvent volume versus Sample volume; (b) Sample volume versus Sample pH; and (c) Elution solvent volume versus Sample pH.

The coefficient of determination (r^2) values ranged from 0.995 to 0.999, meeting the established criterion for this parameter. Regarding MDLs and MQLs, these ranged from 0.07 to 5.04 ng l⁻¹ and from 0.21 to 15.3 ng l⁻¹, respectively. IDL and IQL values were also calculated, with IDL ranging from 0.12 to 35.0 µg l⁻¹, and IQL ranging from 0.36 to 109 µg l⁻¹. These ranges are wide because the values found for MDL and MQL of BMDBM are much higher than those determined for the other analytes. Depending on the analyte, the method was linear from concentrations between 0.21 and 15.3 ng l⁻¹ up to levels between 267 and 333 ng l⁻¹. **Table S4** in the Supplementary Material details the values of retention time, range, r^2 , IDL, IQL, MDL, and MQL for each target analyte.

In order to understand the influence of SW matrix on the detected signal of each compound, the ME was calculated using the optimised SPE conditions (Fig. 5). The results showed both enhancement and suppression of the signal, with variations ranging from -42 to 83 %, depending on the analyte (**Table S5**). The signal is suppressed more prominently for clarithromycin, hydrochlorothiazide, prochloraz, and BMDBM. On contrary, clindamycin, diclofenac, candesartan, irbesartan, fluconazole, miconazole, ipconazole, tebuconazole, 4-methylbenzotriazole, 6-methylbenzotriazole, and benzotriazole exhibited a very low signal suppression. The other compounds demonstrated a signal enhancement, although not very significant in most cases, except for venlafaxine, dimoxystrobin, and metconazole, which showed enhancements of around 66, 58, and 83 %, respectively. Specifically, within the pesticides class, there is a tendency for signal enhancement, excluding ipconazole and prochloraz. Similarly, in the pharmaceuticals class, the

antidepressants (citalopram, venlafaxine, and *O*-desmethylvenlafaxine) displayed the same behaviour, i.e., signal enhancement. Conversely, the signal of UV filters was suppressed, except for octocrylene, which signal was slightly enhanced. Regarding the AR values, ofloxacin, candesartan, prochloraz, BMDBM, and octocrylene exhibited very low recoveries (< 31 %). This can be mainly attributed to the low EEs in the SPE process (**Table S5**), since the MEs were relatively low for those compounds, except for BMDBM. In turn, the other compounds showed higher ARs ranging between 42 and 183 % (**Figure 5**; **Table S5**). Some pharmaceuticals and pesticides showed ARs exceeding 100 %, which can be attributed to the combination of good EEs during the SPE procedure and the enhancement originated by the ME that was typically higher than approximately 20 % for these analytes: venlafaxine, carbamazepine, fipronil, azoxystrobin, dimoxystrobin, metconazole, penconazole, and tetraconazole. The benzotriazoles from the UV filters group had AR values around 70 %, with an almost negligible MEs, showing that the SPE EEs were similar to the ARs. According to European guidelines [30], accuracy can vary between 80–120 %, and this criterion was met for all MPs except for trimethoprim and metconazole, with a close to the upper limit (60 and 79 %, respectively). The precision of the method was assessed through the RSD of replicate analyses, in accordance with international criteria that indicate agreement when the RSD is below 20 %. Thus, only candesartan, irbesartan, azoxystrobin, dimoxystrobin, 4-methyl-benzotriazole, and BMDBM exceeded the intra-batch precision maximum value (21, 22, 21, 45, 21, and 35 %, respectively), but the inter-batch precision values were within the recommended levels.

Fig. 5. Absolute recovery (AR) and matrix effect (ME) of the optimised SPE-UHPLC-MS/MS analytical method for each target compound applying surface water as the matrix – SPE conditions: 375 mL of sample volume, pH of 3–4, and 3.5 mL of EtOH as the elution solvent (# Compounds included in the Watch List 2022, ## Compounds included in the Watch List 2025, * compounds included in the new EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), + compounds included in the proposal for a new list of PSs in Water Framework Directive).

Comparison of the obtained values for method validation parameters with the literature is challenging, as each study focuses on a specific compound or group of compounds and employs different chromatographic and SPE conditions. Therefore, direct comparison between these different conditions is not appropriate. Additionally, significant contradictions and disagreements were found in literature concerning sorbents for each compound group, conditioning and elution protocols and recoveries achieved by the same protocol, which varied depending on the author and the commercial brand of the sorbent. Consequently, no consensus has been reached on the best sorbent and SPE protocol for the isolation, clean-up and concentration of the most frequently analysed groups of compounds, namely pesticides, pharmaceuticals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons [58].

3.4. SPE-LC-MS/MS method application

After validation, the SPE-LC-MS/MS method was applied to SW samples collected from a strategically selected point at the Leça River in northern Portugal (summer 2023). Triplicates of SW samples were analysed to determine the concentration of the 32 target MPs (Fig. 6). Of these compounds, only 9 were not detected in the river water: miconazole, dimoxystrobin, imazalil, metconazole, penconazole, prochloraz, tetraconazole, BMDBM, and octocrylene. Interestingly, except for BMDBM and octocrylene (UV filters class), the remaining undetected compounds are fungicides, mostly included in the pesticides class. Miconazole was the only undetected pharmaceutical fungicide, while other fungicides from this class, namely climbazole and clotrimazole, were detected at very low concentrations ($< 17 \text{ ng l}^{-1}$). Fluconazole, in turn, was detected at concentrations 10 times higher (325 ng l^{-1}). All these compounds are included in the fourth Watch List [17], which highlights their limited monitoring data available to date. Similarly to the pharmaceutical fungicides, detected fungicides categorised as pesticides also registered low concentrations ($< 48 \text{ ng l}^{-1}$), with this class showing poor representativeness in terms of MPs occurrence in the collected water. Still in the pharmaceutical category, the 4 antibiotics clarithromycin,

clindamycin, ofloxacin, and trimethoprim, and the antidepressant citalopram were found below 40 ng l^{-1} . In contrast, *O*-desmethylvenlafaxine, irbesartan, and hydrochlorothiazide were detected at higher concentrations: 1955, 1509, and 2783 ng l^{-1} , respectively. The other target pharmaceuticals (*i.e.*, venlafaxine, amisulpride, diclofenac, carbamazepine, and candesartan) were detected at concentrations ranging from 276 ng l^{-1} to 933 ng l^{-1} . Regarding UV filters, the 3 benzotriazoles were detected: 4-methylbenzotriazole and 6-methylbenzotriazole at considerably lower concentrations (748 and 900 ng l^{-1} , respectively), when compared to benzotriazole which was the MP detected at the highest concentration ($\sim 5000 \text{ ng l}^{-1}$), even when compared to all other target MPs. Although the primary use of benzotriazoles is their application in many products for ultraviolet stabilization, they are also frequently used for metal corrosion inhibition and anti-icing purposes [59]. As such, several studies also describe their frequent detection in different environmental compartments, highlighting their role as CECs in the environment, exhibiting persistent organic pollutants-like characteristics [59–61].

Overall, 72 % of the analytes were detected in the river water samples, confirming the tendency of these compounds to occur in aquatic environments. The compounds listed in the new UWWTD were those detected at higher concentrations (marked with * in Fig. 6), emphasising the need for improved technologies at wastewater treatment plants aiming to remove them and prevent their discharge into waterbodies. According to the new UWWTD, it will be mandatory to monitor these compounds in wastewater treatment plant influents and effluents, and if necessary, implement quaternary treatments to achieve 80 % of removal by 2035 for agglomerations above 100 000 population equivalent [17]. Clarithromycin, diclofenac, and carbamazepine are also listed as PSs in the new proposal for the WFD (marked with + in Fig. 6); however, their concentrations were below the maximum allowable levels for both inland and other SWs, except for clarithromycin in other SWs, which registered 3 ng l^{-1} above the established limit [18]. Among the CECs from the fourth vigilance list [17], most MPs were detected at very low levels, venlafaxine and its metabolite (*O*-desmethylvenlafaxine)

Fig. 6. Concentrations of the target MPs in the Leça River, Portugal. (# Compounds included in the Watch List 2022, ## Compounds included in the Watch List 2025, * compounds included in the new EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD), + compounds included in the proposal for a new list of PSs in Water Framework Directive). Orange circles correspond to MPs with levels below the MDL.

registering the highest concentration, in the order of hundreds and thousands of ng l⁻¹, respectively. Although the relatively lower concentrations of MPs (< 5 µg l⁻¹) may have a low probability of causing immediate adverse effects, the possible long-term effects, especially from exposure to multiple compounds simultaneously (*cocktail effect*), are a concerning issue, the consequences of which are not yet fully understood [62]. However, as abovementioned, chronic effects such as endocrine disruption, microbial resistance to antibiotics, and other toxicological risks for living entities and human health have been documented, highlighting the crucial role of monitoring in supporting risk assessment studies. Thus, the developed method enables the determination of a considerable number of compounds from EU guidelines and will be useful for further studies on the topic. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first optimised and validated method that includes numerous pollutants from recent EU guidelines, for which RSM methodology was also innovatively applied. Data obtained with this method are of utmost importance for gaining insights into the occurrence of these EU relevant MPs. Additionally, they can support regulatory agents in updating legislation, conducting risk assessment exercises, and helping studies on treatment technologies aimed at removing this type of compounds.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of 32 target organic MPs ([M + H]⁺, [M+Na]⁺, and [M-H]⁻) was conducted by SPE-LC-MS/MS using a Kinetex™ 1.7 µm F5 100 Å column at 30 °C, with a gradient of UPW and MeOH, both acidified with 0.1 % formic acid (v/v), and a flow rate of 0.20 mL min⁻¹. Optimal SPE conditions were determined through RSM and involved 375 mL of SW at a pH 3–4, with 3.5 mL of EtOH as the elution solvent. EtOH was chosen for its comparable EE to MeOH and ACN, as well as its lower toxicity, making it a more environmentally friendly option. The values of EE, ME and AR varied widely (8–100 %; –0.15–83 %; 9–183 %, respectively), which is expected given the diverse range of compounds analysed. In general, when compared to other studies, the results varied for the same compounds due to differences in the methodologies used. The developed SPE-LC-MS/MS methodology was validated according to international criteria, with results for selectivity, linearity and range, MDL and MQL, accuracy, recovery, and precision meeting established guidelines. Application of the method to river water samples from northern Portugal revealed the presence of 23 out of 32 MPs, predominantly pharmaceuticals and UV-filters, with fewer pesticides detected, at concentrations ranging from few to thousands of ng l⁻¹. The use of DoE by RSM proved to be a valuable tool for SPE optimisation and should be considered in future studies, even when model fitting is negligible. This study provides significant insights into analytical chemistry applied to environmental samples, as the optimised method can be implemented in monitoring programmes targeting EU organic MPs, helping to generate crucial data on the subject. In this way, it contributes for advancements in water pollution control and ecosystems preservation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ana M. Gorito: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Beatriz R. Mota:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Adrián M.T. Silva:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Ana R.L. Ribeiro:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work is financially supported by national funds through the FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC), under the projects: 2022.02842.PTDC – STAR – STereoselective environmental processes in Antibiotics: role for Resistance (DOI 10.54499/2022.02842.PTDC) (<https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.02842.PTDC>) and 2022.08738.PTDC – DRopH2O – Drinking water quality: early warning and removal of microcontaminants by innovative carbon-based materials (DOI 10.54499/2022.08738.PTDC) (<https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.08738.PTDC>). This research was also supported by: UID/50020 of LSRE-LCM - Laboratory of Separation and Reaction Engineering – Laboratory of Catalysis and Materials - funded by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. /MCTES through national funds; and ALiCe - LA/P/0045/2020 (DOI: 10.54499/LA/P/0045/2020). In addition, this study was funded by ERA-ARE (ERC-2021-STG) supported by the European Commission through the European Research Council Executive Agency under the project 101039270. *Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.* ARLR acknowledges FCT funding under the Scientific Employment Stimulus - Individual Call (Ref. 2022.00184.CEECIND/CP1733/CT0001, DOI 10.54499/2022.00184.CEECIND/CP1733/CT0001, <https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.00184.CEECIND/CP1733/CT0001>).

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2025.466052](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2025.466052).

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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